
CHARACTERIZATION OF A-DISTRIBUTIVE SEMILATTICES

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Abstract:

In this paper, we defined a-distributive semilattice and obtain properties of a-distributive semilattice in terms of a-ideals and \hat{a} -filter. Also we have obtain several characterizations of a-distributive semilattice.

Key Words: a-distributive semilattice , a-ideals , \hat{a} -filter

Introduction:

0-distributive lattice concept introduced by Varlet. Then P. Balasubramani and P. Venkatanarasimhan have obtain many characterizations with the help of ideal, filter , prime ideal , minimal prime ideal etc. A lattice L with 0 is called a 0-distributive lattice if for all a, b, c $\in L$ with $a \wedge b = 0$ and $a \wedge c = 0$ imply $a \wedge (b \vee c) = 0$. Any distributive lattice with 0 is 0 - distributive. In this paper we will study the a-distributive meet Semilattices. Y. S. Pawar and M. V. Patil introduced the concept a - distributive lattice for any fixed element $a \neq 1$ in bounded lattice. Also defined a-ideal, prime a-ideal, minimal prime a-ideal and \hat{a} -filter, etc. and obtain many

characterization. Any a - distributive lattice is 0 – distributive. In this paper we generalized concept a-distributive lattices to a-distributive semi lattices. Also we introduced a-ideal, prima-ideal, minimal prime a-ideal and \hat{a} -filter in a-distributive semi lattices.

Let S be a meet semilattice with 0. Let a, b, c in S be such that whenever $\mathbf{b} \vee \mathbf{c}$ exists, $\mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{0}$ imply $\mathbf{a} \wedge (\mathbf{b} \vee \mathbf{c}) = \mathbf{0}$, then S is called 0-distributive semilattice. We generalized a-distributive semi lattice as x, y, z, a ($a \neq 1$) in S be such that whenever $\mathbf{y} \vee \mathbf{z}$ exists, $\mathbf{x} \wedge \mathbf{y} \leq \mathbf{a}$ and $\mathbf{x} \wedge \mathbf{z} \leq \mathbf{a}$ imply $\mathbf{x} \wedge (\mathbf{y} \vee \mathbf{z}) \leq \mathbf{a}$.

The Hasse figure given below is example of a-Distributive Semilattice.

Fig. 1

The following figure shows that a-distributive semilattice need not be distributive.

Fig. 2

The following figure is example of semilattice is not a-distributive.

Fig. 3

An ideal I in S is a non-empty subset of S such that $a \leq b, b \in I$ implies $a \in I$ and whenever avb exists for a, b in I

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then $a \vee b \in I$. (see Venkatanarasimhan [1]). A proper ideal I in S is called prime if $x \wedge y \in I$ implies that either $x \in I$ or $y \in I$.

Varlet [5] has generalized the concept of maximal filters and introduce a a -maximal filter in L . Thus maximal a -filter in M is a filter in L which is maximal with respect to not containing the given fixed element $a (\neq 1)$ in L . An a -filter is a filter in L not containing a . In this chapter we introduce the concepts of semi a -ideal, a -ideal, prime semi a -ideal and minimal prime a -ideal etc. in S . We begin with simple but essential concepts.

Definition and Properties:

Definition 2. 1: - A non-empty subset I of S is semi-ideal in L if $x \leq y, y \in I$ imply $x \in I$ for x, y in S .

Definition 2.2: - A semi-ideal in S containing the element a is called semi a -ideal.

Definition 2. 3: - A prime semi-ideal in S containing the element a is called prime semi a -ideal.

Definition 2.4: - An ideal in S which is maximal w. r. t containing the element a is called maximal a -ideal.

Definition 2.5:- Minimal element in the set of all prime a -ideals in S is called minimal prime a -ideal.

Note that for $a = 0$ in particular, the above definitions 1 to 5 coincide with the usual definitions of semi-ideal, prime semi-ideal, maximal ideal, minimal prime ideal respectively (see Venkatanarasimhan [1]).

We begin with a rather elementary result the easy proof of which is omitted.

While proving the properties of prime semi ideals, Venkatanarasimhan [1] has proved that, a nonempty subset F ($F \neq 1$) of L is filter if and only if $(L \setminus F)$ is prime semi-ideal.

More generally, we prove

Theorem 2.1: - A non-empty subset F of S ($F \neq 1$) is \hat{a} -filter if and only if $(S \setminus F)$ is prime semi \hat{a} -ideal.

Proof:- only if part.

Let F be \hat{a} -filter in S . As $a \notin F$ we get $a \in (S \setminus F)$. Hence $(S \setminus F)$ is non-empty. Let $x \leq y$ and $y \in (S \setminus F)$. Suppose $x \notin (S \setminus F)$ we get $x \in F$. But as F is filter we get $y \in F$; a contradiction. Therefore $x \in (S \setminus F)$. Hence $(S \setminus F)$ is semi \hat{a} -ideal in S .

If $x \wedge y \in (S \setminus F)$ then $x \wedge y \notin F$. As F is filter, either $x \notin F$ or $y \notin F$. Thus $x \in (S \setminus F)$ or $y \in (S \setminus F)$. This shows $(S \setminus F)$ is prime semi \hat{a} -ideal.

If part.

Let $(S \setminus F)$ be prime semi \hat{a} -ideal in L . To prove that F is \hat{a} -filter.

(i) As $a \in (S \setminus F)$ we get $a \notin F$ and hence F is non-empty.

(ii) Let $x \leq y$ and $x \in F$. Suppose $y \notin F$. Then we get $y \in (S \setminus F)$. But as $(S \setminus F)$ is semi ideal we get $x \in (S \setminus F)$; a contradiction. Thus $y \in F$.

(iii) Let $x, y \in F$. Then $x, y \notin (S \setminus F)$. As $(S \setminus F)$ is prime semi ideal we get $x \wedge y \notin (S \setminus F)$ i.e. $x \wedge y \in F$. From (i), (ii) and (iii) we get F is filter in S . As $a \notin F$ we get F is \hat{a} -filter.

Theorem 2.2:- Any \hat{a} -filter in S is contained in some maximal \hat{a} -filter.

Proof:- Let F be \hat{a} -filter in S . Define $K = \{J \mid J \text{ is an } \hat{a}\text{-filter in } L \text{ containing } F\}$. As $F \in K$ we get K is non-empty. Let ξ be any chain in K and $X = \cup C \in \xi$. Then obviously, X is filter in S as X is union of members of chain of filters in S . Further as $F \subseteq X$ and $a \notin X$.

We get $X \in K$. By Zorn's Lemma, there exists a maximal element M in K . This M is maximal \hat{a} -filter containing F .

Theorem 2.3:- Let F be \hat{a} -filter in S . Then F is maximal \hat{a} -filter if and only if for $x \notin F$ there exists $y \in F$ such that $x \wedge y \leq a$.

Proof:- Only if Part.

Let F be maximal \hat{a} -filter in S and $x \notin F$.

Then $F \vee [x]$ is filter such that $F \subset F \vee [x]$. But as F is maximal \hat{a} -filter we get $a \in F \vee [x]$. This implies $a \geq x \wedge y$ for some $y \in F$ and the result follows.

If Part.

Let F be any \hat{a} -filter in S satisfying the condition in the statement. Now we prove F is maximal \hat{a} -filter in S . Let if possible there exists \hat{a} -filter J in L such that $F \subset J \subsetneq S$. As $F \subset J$, there exists $x \in J$ such that $x \notin F$. By assumption, there exists $y \in F$ such that $x \wedge y \leq a$. Now $F \subset J$ and $y \in F$ imply $y \in J$. As $x \in J, y \in J$ we get $a \in J$; a contradiction. Hence F is maximal \hat{a} -filter in S .

Characterizations:-

In the following theorem we characterize a -distributive lattices in terms of a -ideals in S .

Theorem 3. 1:- The following statements are equivalent in S .

1. S is a -distributive semi lattice.
2. If x, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n in L such that $x \wedge y_i \leq a, \forall i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, then $x \wedge [y_1 \vee y_2 \vee \dots \vee y_n] \leq a$ if $y_1 \vee y_2 \vee \dots \vee y_n$ exists.
3. If A is a -ideal and $\{A_i \mid i \in I\}$ is a family of a -ideals such that $A \cap A_i \subseteq (a]$, for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$, then $A \cap [\vee_{i \in I} A_i] \subseteq (a]$.

Proof:-

(1) \Rightarrow (2)

As S is a -distributive, the result is true for $n = 2$. Using the induction on n , the implication follows.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) let a be a -ideal and $\{a_i \mid i \in I\}$ be a family of a -ideals such that

$A \cap A_i \subseteq (a]$, for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$. If $x \in a \cap [\vee_{i \in I} a_i]$, then $x \in a$ and $x \in \vee_{i \in I} A_i$. As $x \in \vee_{i \in I} A_i$ we get $x \leq y_1 \vee y_2 \vee \dots \vee y_n$ for some finite n with $y_i \in a_i$ for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$ if $y_1 \vee y_2 \vee \dots \vee y_n$ exists. As $x \in A$ and $y_i \in A_i$ we get $x \wedge y_i \in A \cap A_i \subseteq (a]$.

Therefore $x \wedge y_i \leq a$, for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq n$.

Hence by assumption (2), $x \wedge [y_1 \vee y_2 \vee \dots \vee y_n] \leq a$.

Thus $x \leq a$. This shows $A \cap [\vee_{i \in I} A_i] \subseteq (a]$ and the implication follow.

(3) \Rightarrow (1)

To prove that S is a -distributive. Let $x \wedge y \leq a, x \wedge z \leq a$ for

x, y, z in S . But this turn imply $(x] \wedge (y] \subseteq (a]$ and

$(x] \wedge (z] \subseteq (a]$. By assumption (3), we get

$(x] \wedge ((y] \vee (z]) \subseteq (a]$. Thus $x \wedge (y \vee z) \leq a$ as

$(x] \wedge ((y] \vee (z]) = (x \wedge (y \vee z))]$.

Hence S is a -distributive lattice.

Thus (1) \Rightarrow (2) \Rightarrow (3) \Rightarrow (1) shows

that all the statements are equivalent .

Theorem 3. 2:- S is a - distributive if and only if every maximal \hat{a} - filter is prime.

Proof:- Only if Part .

Let S be a - distributive semilattice and M be any maximal \hat{a} - filter .

To prove M is prime . Let if possible there exist x, y in L such that $x \vee y \in M$ with $x \notin M$ and $y \notin M$. As M is maximal \hat{a} - filter, $a \in M \vee [x)$ and $a \in M \vee [y)$. Then $a \geq m_1 \wedge x$ and $a \geq m_2 \wedge y$ for some $m_1, m_2 \in M$. But then $a \geq m_1 \wedge m_2 \wedge x$ and $a \geq m_1 \wedge m_2 \wedge y$ will imply $a \geq (m_1 \wedge m_2) \wedge (x \vee y)$ by a-distributive of S . But as $m_1 \wedge m_2 \in M$ and $x \vee y \in M$ we get $a \in M$; a contradiction. Thus $x \vee y \in M$ must imply $x \in M$ or $y \in M$. This proves that M is prime.

If Part.

Assume that every maximal \hat{a} - filter in S is prime. To prove that S is a - distributive semi lattice. Let if possible there exist x, y, z in S such that $x \wedge y \leq a, x \wedge z \leq a$ with $x \wedge (y \vee z) \not\leq a$. Define $F = [x \wedge (y \vee z)$. Obviously, F is \hat{a} - filter in S . By Theorem 1.2.7, F is contained in some maximal \hat{a} - filter say M .But then $x \wedge (y \vee z) \in M$ imply $x \in M$ and $y \vee z \in M$.M being prime , we get $x \wedge y \in M$ or $x \wedge z \in M$.

But in either the case $a \in M$; a contradiction. Hence $x \wedge y \leq a, x \wedge z \leq a$ imply $x \wedge (y \vee z) \leq a$ for x, y, z in S . Hence L is a - distributive lattice.

□□□

A lattice L is distributive if and only if for $x < y$ in L there exists a prime filter F containing x but not y . (see Gratzner [2] , page 78) . In the following theorem we prove a similar characterization for a - distributive semi lattice.

Theorem 3. .3:- L is a - distributive if and only if for $x \not\leq a$ in L , there exists prime \hat{a} - filter containing x .

Proof:- Only if Part .

Let L be a - distributive lattice and $x \not\leq a$ for some x in S. As $[x)$ is \hat{a} - filter . By Theorem 1.2.7, $[x)$ is contained in maximal \hat{a} - filter say M. S being a - distributive, M is prime \hat{a} - filter. This shows the existence of prime \hat{a} - filter M containing x.

If Part .

Suppose L is not a - distributive. Hence there exist x, y, z in L such that $x \wedge y \leq a, x \wedge z \leq a$ with $x \wedge (y \vee z) \not\leq a$. By hypothesis, there exists prime \hat{a} - filter P containing $x \wedge (y \vee z)$. Then we get $x \wedge y \in P$ or $x \wedge z \in P$; P being prime \hat{a} - filter . But in either the case $a \in P$, contradicting the choice of P.

Thus $x \wedge y \leq a$, $x \wedge z \leq a$ must imply $x \wedge (y \vee z) \leq a$ for all x, y, z in L . Hence S is a a – distributive semi lattice.

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